

RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

doi: <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00086>

'FAIR, CARE, TRUST - Principles'

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://rd-alliance.org/rdas-20th-plenary-pathways>

Version: March 2023

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

The FAIR, CARE and TRUST principles and their applicability to various research objects, including data, software, metadata and hardware.

RDA 20th PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 3: FAIR for Machine Learning (FAIR4ML) IG: [Defining the roadmap towards FAIR for Machine Learning](#)
- Breakout 4: Software Source Code IG: [Software Source Code - policy and incentives](#)
- Breakout 5: FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG: [IG FAIR Digital Object Fabric: Discussing the FAIR DO Concept](#)
- Breakout 7: RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG: [TRUST Principles & Certification updates](#)
- Breakout 7: FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG: [Draft recommendations for making VREs FAIR and FAIR-enabling](#)

[View the Plenary programme](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#)
- [A Fresh Look at FAIR for Research Software](#)
- [A Survey on Adoption Guidelines for the FAIR4RS Principles](#)
- [Array Database Assessment Recommendations](#)
- [Challenges of Curating for Reproducible and FAIR Research Output](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model specification and guidelines](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software \(FAIR4RS Principles\)](#)
- [FAIR4RS Adoption support](#)
- [Health Research Performing Organisations \(HRPOs\) FAIR Guidelines](#)
- [RDA Data Usage Metrics WG Recommendations](#)
- [Summary of Virtual Layer Recommendations](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
- [Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things](#)
- [Use cases and identifier schemes for persistent software source code identification \(V1.1\)](#)

[See all recommendations & outputs](#)

RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Blockchain Applications in Health WG](#)
- [CURE-FAIR WG](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model WG](#)
- [FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG](#)
- [FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\) WG](#)
- [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Hardware](#)
- [International Indigenous Data Sovereignty IG](#)
- [PID IG](#)
- [Raising FAIRness in health data and health research performing organisations \(HRPOs\) WG](#)
- [RDA COVID-19](#)
- [RDA Privacy Implications of Research Data Sets IG](#)
- [RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG](#)
- [Reproducible Health Data Services WG](#)
- [Social Science Research Data IG](#)
- [Software Source Code IG](#)
- [Virtual Research Environment IG \(VRE-IG\)](#)

[See all RDA groups](#)

RDA DOMAIN AMBASSADOR

Allyson Lister

RDA/EOSC Future Domain Ambassador for standards, repositories and policies

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RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

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'FAIR, CARE, TRUST - Adoption, Implementation & Deployment'

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://rd-alliance.org/rdas-20th-plenary-pathways>

Version: March 2023

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Practices and methods for the adoption, implementation and deployment of the FAIR, CARE and TRUST Principles.

RDA 20th PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 1: Birds of a Feather: [Coordinating mechanisms for making code visible](#)
- Breakout 2: National PID Strategies WG: [Pathways to a national PID strategy: a guide to facilitate uptake and alignment](#)
- Breakout 2: Life Science Data Infrastructures IG & FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG: [Infrastructure supporting the FAIR data principles in life science research practice](#)
- Breakout 3: Birds of a Feather: [Computational Reproducibility: What's Next for RDA?](#)
- Breakout 4: Birds of a Feather: [Promoting synergies between national RDM and data stewardship networks](#)
- Breakout 4: Education and Training on Handling of Research Data IG: [From Classroom to Practice: integrating education and training in handling research data](#)
- Breakout 4: FAIR Data Maturity Model WG & Persistent Identification of Instruments WG: [The Way to FAIR: from data collection to citation](#)
- Breakout 5: Data for Development IG & RDA for the Sustainable Development Goals IG: [Data for Sustainable Development \(SD\) and Responsible Research \(RR\)](#)
- Breakout 5: Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology WG (I-ADOPT WG): [Practical implementations of the I-ADOPT framework and future directions](#)
- Breakout 6: Brokering Framework WG: [Brokering Framework - Update and Finalisation](#)

- Breakout 6: Birds of a Feather: [Trusted Research Environments for Sensitive Data: FAIRness for "Closed" Data and Processes](#)
- Breakout 7: RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG: [TRUST Principles & Certification updates](#)
- Breakout 7: FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG: [Draft recommendations for making VREs FAIR and FAIR-enabling](#)
- Breakout 7: Data Granularity WG: [Data Granularity Guidance - Going Once, Going Twice....](#)
- Breakout 7: IGAD Community of Practice: [Improving Global Agricultural Data \(IGAD\) Community of Practice First Steps and Way Forward](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Blockchain Applications in Health WG](#)
- [Brokering Framework Working Group](#)
- [CURE-FAIR WG](#)
- [Data Conservation IG](#)
- [Data for Development IG](#)
- [Data Granularity WG](#)
- [Data policy standardisation and implementation IG](#)
- [Education and Training on Handling of Research Data IG](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model WG](#)
- [FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG](#)
- [FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\) WG](#)
- [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Hardware](#)
- [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG](#)
- [Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology WG \(I-ADOPT WG\)](#)
- [Libraries for Research Data IG](#)
- [Life Science Data Infrastructures IG](#)
- [National PID Strategies WG](#)
- [PID IG](#)

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Practices and methods for the adoption, implementation and deployment of the FAIR, CARE and TRUST Principles.

RELEVANT RDA GROUPS CONT.

- [Preservation Tools, Techniques, and Policies](#)
- [Preserving Scientific Annotation WG](#)
- [Professionalising Data Stewardship IG](#)
- [Raising FAIRness in health data and health research performing organisations \(HRPOs\) WG](#)
- [RDA COVID19-Legal-Ethical](#)
- [RDA/CODATA Legal Interoperability IG](#)
- [RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG](#)
- [Repository Core Description WG](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Software](#)
- [RDA for the Sustainable Development Goals IG](#)
- [Reproducible Health Data Services WG](#)
- [Research Metadata Schemas WG](#)
- [Skills and training curriculums to support FAIR research software IG](#)
- [Social Dynamics of Data Interoperability IG](#)
- [Virtual Research Environment IG \(VRE-IG\)](#)

✨ [See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#)
- [A Fresh Look at FAIR for Research Software](#)
- [A Survey on Adoption Guidelines for the FAIR4RS Principles](#)
- [Challenges of Curating for Reproducible and FAIR Research Output](#)
- [Data Discovery Paradigms User Requirements and Recommendations for Data Repositories](#)
- [Developing a Research Data Policy Framework for All Journals and Publishers](#)
- [Eleven Quick Tips for Finding Research Data](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software \(FAIR4RS Principles\)](#)
- [FAIR4RS Adoption support](#)
- [Health Research Performing Organisations \(HRPOs\) FAIR Guidelines](#)
- [Income Streams for Data Repositories](#)
- [Member survey on bridging the gap - perspectives on benefits and challenges of FAIR assessments V2.0](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS CONT.

- [Principles and best practices in data versioning for all data sets big and small](#)
- [RDA & CODATA Legal Interoperability Of Research Data Principles And Implementation Guidelines](#)
- [RDA Data Usage Metrics WG Recommendations](#)
- [Recommendations and Capacity Development Resource Kit](#)
- [Research Data Repository Interoperability Primer](#)
- [Research Data Repository Interoperability WG Final Recommendations](#)
- [Summary of Virtual Layer Recommendations](#)
- [Sustainable Business Models for Brokering Middleware to support Research Interoperability](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
- [The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies](#)
- [Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things](#)
- [Use cases and identifier schemes for persistent software source code identification \(V1.1\)](#)
- [WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG Outputs and Recommendations](#)

📄 [See all recommendations & outputs](#)

RDA DOMAIN AMBASSADOR

Sara El-Gebali

RDA/EOSC Future Domain Ambassador for Life Science

📖 [Read more & contact](#)

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RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

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'Data Infrastructures & Environments - Institutional'

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://rd-alliance.org/rdas-20th-plenary-pathways>

Version: March 2023

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Workflows and methods to implement the FAIR, CARE and TRUST Principles at the institutional data infrastructure level.

RDA 20th PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 3: Sensitive Data Interest Group: [Sensitive data contexts and disciplines: A look at different approaches](#)
- Breakout 5: Data Citation WG: [Adoption Meeting of the WG on Dynamic Data Citation](#)
- Breakout 5: Birds of a Feather: [Exploring User-Centered Services for Collections as Data at the Library of Congress](#)
- Breakout 6: ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences IG: [Continuing the Circle of Life of Earth and Environmental Science Data Infrastructure Projects: Maturing PARSEC and ENVRI-FAIR, Beginning New Adventures](#)
- Breakout 6: Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions IG: [The Role of Middleware in Data and Metadata Management: National and Institutional Approaches Involving iRODS and Alternatives](#)
- Breakout 6: Birds of a Feather: [Trusted Research Environments for Sensitive Data: FAIRness for "Closed" Data and Processes](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS CONT.

- [Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions IG](#)
- [Research data needs of the Photon and Neutron Science community IG](#)
- [Sensitive Data Interest Group](#)
- [Skills and training curriculums to support FAIR research software IG](#)
- [Software Source Code IG](#)

★ [See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [A Fresh Look at FAIR for Research Software](#)
- [Array Database Assessment Recommendations](#)
- [Challenges of Curating for Reproducible and FAIR Research Output](#)
- [Data Discovery Paradigms User Requirements and Recommendations for Data Repositories](#)
- [Eleven Quick Tips for Finding Research Data](#)
- [Income Streams for Data Repositories](#)
- [RDA COVID-19 Guidelines and Recommendations \(draft versions\)](#)
- [RDA Data Usage Metrics WG Recommendations](#)
- [Report prepared at Plenary 3](#)
- [Summary of Virtual Layer Recommendations](#)
- [Sustainable Business Models for Brokering Middleware to support Research Interoperability](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
- [The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies](#)
- [Use cases and identifier schemes for persistent software source code identification \(V1.1\)](#)

 [See all recommendations & outputs](#)

RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Complex Citations Working Group](#)
- [Data Citation WG](#)
- [Domain Repositories IG](#)
- [ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences IG](#)
- [Preservation Tools, Techniques, and Policies](#)
- [Repository Core Description WG](#)
- [Repository Platforms for Research Data IG](#)

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A Decade of Data 2013-2023
Research Data Alliance

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'Data Infrastructures & Environments - Regional and Disciplinary'

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://rd-alliance.org/rdas-20th-plenary-pathways>

Version: March 2023

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Standards and practices specific to a region and disciplinary community.

RDA 20th PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 1: Social Science Research Data IG: [SSIG plenary meeting - Growing international coordination across social science infrastructures](#)
- Breakout 2: Life Science Data Infrastructures IG & FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG: [Infrastructure supporting the FAIR data principles in life science research practice](#)
- Breakout 2: Working with PIDS in Tools: [Working with PIDS in Tools and e-infrastructures: Three concrete examples](#)
- Breakout 2: Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (AIDV) WG: [The Ethics of AI and Data Visitation: Building Blocks for Data Commons and Open Science](#)
- Breakout 2: RDA/CODATA Materials Data, Infrastructure & Interoperability IG & Research Data Management in Engineering IG: [Automation of LIMS for Data Analysis and Reuse: Joint Meeting](#)
- Breakout 3: Physical Samples and Collections in the Research Data Ecosystem IG: [Expanding our horizons to new disciplines: harmonising on what is core to all](#)
- Breakout 4: FAIR Data Maturity Model WG & Persistent Identification of Instruments WG: [The Way to FAIR: from data collection to citation](#)
- Breakout 5: Data for Development IG & RDA for the Sustainable Development Goals IG: [Data for Sustainable Development \(SD\) and Responsible Research \(RR\)](#)
- Breakout 6: Data Discovery Paradigms: [Recommendations for data repositories to improve data discoverability](#)

- Breakout 6: ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences IG: [Continuing the Circle of Life of Earth and Environmental Science Data Infrastructure Projects: Maturing PARSEC and ENVRI-FAIR, Beginning New Adventures](#)
- Breakout 7: Chemistry Research Data IG: [Describing diverse chemistry datasets across distributed data resources](#)
- Breakout 7: FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG: [Draft recommendations for making VREs FAIR and FAIR-enabling](#)
- Breakout 7: IGAD Community of Practice: [Improving Global Agricultural Data \(IGAD\) Community of Practice First Steps and Way Forward](#)
- Breakout 7: Open Science Graphs for FAIR Data IG: [Open Science Graph - Interoperability Framework. A debriefing from the Task Force](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG](#)
- [Chemistry Research Data IG](#)
- [Data Discovery Paradigms IG](#)
- [ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences IG](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model WG](#)
- [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG](#)
- [Life Science Data Infrastructures IG](#)
- [Physical Samples and Collections in the Research Data Ecosystem IG](#)
- [Repository Platforms for Research Data IG](#)
- [Social Science Research Data IG](#)
- [Agrisemantics WG](#)
- [Capacity Development for Agriculture Data WG](#)
- [Geospatial IG](#)
- [Global Water Information IG](#)
- [Health Data Interest Group](#)
- [Psychological Data IG](#)

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Data Infrastructures & Environments - Regional and Disciplinary cont.

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://rd-alliance.org/rdas-20th-plenary-pathways>

Version: March 2023

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Standards and practices specific to a region and disciplinary community.

RELEVANT RDA GROUPS CONT.

- [RDA COVID-19](#)
- [RDA COVID-19 Epidemiology](#)
- [RDA COVID19-Legal-Ethical](#)
- [RDA/CODATA Summer Schools in Data Science and Cloud Computing in the Developing World WG](#)
- [RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG](#)
- [Repository Core Description WG](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Clinical](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Community-participation](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Omics](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Social-Sciences](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Software](#)
- [Reproducible Health Data Services WG](#)
- [Research Data Management in Engineering IG](#)
- [Research data needs of the Photon and Neutron Science community IG](#)
- [Virtual Research Environment IG \(VRE-IG\)](#)
- [Working with PIDS in Tools](#)

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RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#)
- [23 Things Physical Samples](#)
- [A Fresh Look at FAIR for Research Software](#)
- [Challenges of Curating for Reproducible and FAIR Research Output](#)
- [Data Discovery Paradigms User Requirements and Recommendations for Data Repositories](#)
- [Eleven Quick Tips for Finding Research Data](#)
- [Health Research Performing Organisations \(HRPOs\) FAIR Guidelines](#)
- [Income Streams for Data Repositories](#)
- [Report prepared at Plenary 3](#)
- [Summary of Virtual Layer Recommendations](#)

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'Data Infrastructures & Environments - International'

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://rd-alliance.org/rdas-20th-plenary-pathways>

Version: March 2023

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Topics related to implementing principles that are common to all data infrastructures and community practices.

RDA 20th PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 1: GORC International Model WG (GORC-IM WG) & Global Open Research Commons IG: [GORC International Model WG Reflections and Document Development, The EOSC Finnish Forum and the Nordic implementations of research commons](#)
- Breakout 1: Data Usage Metrics WG & Repository Platforms for Research Data IG: [Practical Approaches to Tracking and Communicating the Use of Research Data](#)
- Breakout 1: Birds of a Feather: [Coordinating mechanisms for making code visible](#)
- Breakout 1: Social Science Research Data IG: [SSIG plenary meeting - Growing international coordination across social science infrastructures](#)
- Breakout 2: National PID Strategies WG: [Pathways to a national PID strategy: a guide to facilitate uptake and alignment](#)
- Breakout 2: Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (AIDV) WG: [The Ethics of AI and Data Visitation: Building Blocks for Data Commons and Open Science](#)
- Breakout 2: RDA/CODATA Materials Data, Infrastructure & Interoperability IG & Research Data Management in Engineering IG: [Automation of LIMS for Data Analysis and Reuse: Joint Meeting](#)
- Breakout 3: Physical Samples and Collections in the Research Data Ecosystem IG: [Expanding our horizons to new disciplines: harmonising on what is core to all](#)
- Breakout 3: Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Complex Citations Working Group: [Complex Citations in the Earth and Space Sciences: Formulating Requirements for a Demonstration Prototype](#)

- Breakout 5: WG Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology WG (I-ADOPT WG): [Practical implementations of the I-ADOPT framework and future directions](#)
- Breakout 5: FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG, Professionalising Data Stewardship IG, Early Career and Engagement IG & Engaging Researchers with Data IG: [Community Engagement That Works! Examining tools and success stories of pathways to Engagement in Community-led organisations at a global level](#)
- Breakout 5: FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG: IG FAIR Digital Object Fabric: [Discussing the FAIR DO Concept](#)
- Breakout 6: Data Discovery Paradigms: [Recommendations for data repositories to improve data discoverability](#)
- Breakout 6: ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences IG: [Continuing the Circle of Life of Earth and Environmental Science Data Infrastructure Projects: Maturing PARSEC and ENVRI-FAIR, Beginning New Adventures](#)
- Breakout 6: WG Data Repository Attributes WG: [Data Repository Attributes Working Group \(DRAWG\) Working Meeting](#)
- Breakout 7: Open Science Graphs for FAIR Data IG: [Open Science Graph - Interoperability Framework. A debriefing from the Task Force](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG](#)
- [Brokering Framework Working Group](#)

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'Data Infrastructures & Environments - International' cont.

Research Data Alliance Pathways

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THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Topics related to implementing principles that are common to all data infrastructures and community practices.

RELEVANT RDA GROUPS CONT.

- [Complex Citations Working Group](#)
- [Data Discovery Paradigms IG](#)
- [Data for Development IG](#)
- [Data Granularity WG](#)
- [Data Repository Attributes WG](#)
- [Data Usage Metrics WG](#)
- [Domain Repositories IG](#)
- [ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences IG](#)
- [FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG](#)
- [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG](#)
- [Global Open Research Commons IG](#)
- [GORC International Model WG](#)
- [Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology WG \(I-ADOPT WG\)](#)
- [Life Science Data Infrastructures IG](#)
- [National PID Strategies WG](#)
- [Physical Samples and Collections in the Research Data Ecosystem IG](#)
- [PID IG](#)
- [Preservation Tools, Techniques, and Policies](#)
- [Preserving Scientific Annotation WG](#)
- [RDA Privacy Implications of Research Data Sets IG](#)
- [RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG](#)
- [Repository Core Description WG](#)
- [Repository Platforms for Research Data IG](#)
- [Research data needs of the Photon and Neutron Science community IG](#)
- [Social Dynamics of Data Interoperability IG](#)
- [Social Science Research Data IG](#)
- [Software Source Code IG](#)
- [Virtual Research Environment IG \(VRE-IG\)](#)
- [Working Group on Ethical and Legal best practices for Drone Data in a global research context \(WELDD\)](#)

☀ [See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#)
- [A Fresh Look at FAIR for Research Software](#)
- [A Survey on Adoption Guidelines for the FAIR4RS Principles](#)
- [Array Database Assessment Recommendations](#)
- [Challenges of Curating for Reproducible and FAIR Research Output](#)
- [Data Discovery Paradigms User Requirements and Recommendations for Data Repositories](#)
- [Eleven Quick Tips for Finding Research Data](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software \(FAIR4RS Principles\)](#)
- [FAIR4RS Adoption support](#)
- [Income Streams for Data Repositories](#)
- [Member survey on bridging the gap between funders and communities - perspectives on benefits and challenges of FAIR assessments V2.0](#)
- [RDA Data Usage Metrics WG Recommendations](#)
- [Report prepared at Plenary 3](#)
- [Summary of Virtual Layer Recommendations](#)
- [Sustainable Business Models for Brokering Middleware to support Research Interoperability](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
- [The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies](#)
- [Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things](#)
- [Use cases and identifier schemes for persistent software source code identification \(V1.1\)](#)

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'Training, Stewardship & Data Management Planning'

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://rd-alliance.org/rdas-20th-plenary-pathways>

Version: March 2023

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Training modules, schools, workshops and library support for stewardship and data management.

RDA 20th PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 1: CODATA/RDA Research Data Science Schools for Low and Middle Income Countries: [Operationalising the CODATA-RDA Schools of Research Data Science \(SoRDS\)](#)
- Breakout 1: Active Data Management Plans IG , DMP Common Standards WG , & Discipline-specific Guidance for Data Management Plans WG: [Data Management Planning: where are we and where do we want to be?](#)
- Breakout 3: Birds of a Feather: [Computational Reproducibility: What's Next for RDA?](#)
- Breakout 4: Birds of a Feather: [Promoting synergies between national RDM and data stewardship networks](#)
- Breakout 4: CODATA/RDA Research Data Science Schools for Low and Middle Income Countries: [CODATA-RDA Schools for Research Data Science group updates and new challenges](#)
- Breakout 4: FAIR Data Maturity Model WG , Persistent Identification of Instruments WG: [The Way to FAIR: from data collection to citation](#)
- Breakout 5: Data Citation WG: [Adoption Meeting of the WG on Dynamic Data Citation](#)
- Breakout 5: Birds of a Feather: [Exploring User-Centered Services for Collections as Data at the Library of Congress](#)
- Breakout 6: Libraries for Research Data IG: [Libraries' Role in Supporting UNESCO Open Science Recommendations](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Active Data Management Plans IG](#)
- [DMP Common Standards WG](#)
- [CODATA/RDA Research Data Science Schools for Low and Middle Income Countries](#)
- [CURE-FAIR WG](#)
- [Discipline-specific Guidance for Data Management Plans WG](#)
- [Early Career and Engagement IG](#)
- [Engaging Researchers with Data IG](#)
- [Exposing Data Management Plans WG](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model WG](#)
- [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG](#)
- [Libraries for Research Data IG](#)
- [Professionalising Data Stewardship IG](#)
- [Psychological Data Community of Practice](#)
- [RDA Privacy Implications of Research Data Sets IG](#)
- [RDA/CODATA Summer Schools in Data Science and Cloud Computing in the Developing World WG](#)
- [Research Data Management in Engineering IG](#)
- [Skills and training curriculums to support FAIR research software IG](#)

✨ [See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [23 Things Libraries for Research Data](#)
- [Core Characteristics of Learning Resource Collectors](#)
- [Engaging Researchers with Data Management The Cookbook](#)
- [Member survey on bridging the gap between funders and communities - perspectives on benefits and challenges of FAIR assessments V2.0](#)
- [RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship - Data Stewardship Landscape Initial Report](#)
- [Recommendations for a minimal metadata set to aid harmonised discovery of learning resources](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
- [The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies](#)

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Research Data Alliance

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Standardisation of metadata profiles, semantics and ontologies for maximising interoperability.

RDA 20th PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 1: Vocabulary Services IG: [What is happening in the Semantic interoperability realm and in VSSIG?](#)
- Breakout 2: National PID Strategies WG: [Pathways to a national PID strategy: a guide to facilitate uptake and alignment](#)
- Breakout 2: Working with PIDS in Tools: [Working with PIDS in Tools and e-infrastructures: Three concrete examples](#)
- Breakout 3: FAIR for Machine Learning (FAIR4ML) IG: [Defining the roadmap towards FAIR for Machine Learning](#)
- Breakout 3: Birds of a Feather: [Data representation in materials and chemicals based on harmonised domain ontologies](#)
- Breakout 3: Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Complex Citations Working Group: [Complex Citations in the Earth and Space Sciences: Formulating Requirements for a Demonstration Prototype](#)
- Breakout 4: Data policy standardisation and implementation IG: [Increasing the positive impacts of journal policies on data sharing practices](#)
- Breakout 5: Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology WG (I-ADOPT WG): [Practical implementations of the I-ADOPT framework and future directions](#)
- Breakout 6: Brokering Framework Working Group: [Brokering Framework - Update and Finalisation](#)
- Breakout 7: Chemistry Research Data IG: [Describing diverse chemistry datasets across distributed data resources](#)
- Breakout 7: Data Granularity WG: [Data Granularity Guidance - Going Once, Going Twice,...](#)

- Breakout 7: Open Science Graphs for FAIR Data IG: [Open Science Graph - Interoperability Framework. A debriefing from the Task Force](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Agrisemantics WG](#)
- [Blockchain Applications in Health WG](#)
- [Brokering Framework Working Group](#)
- [Complex Citations Working Group](#)
- [Chemistry Research Data IG](#)
- [Data Granularity WG](#)
- [Data policy standardisation and implementation IG](#)
- [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG](#)
- [FAIR for Machine Learning \(FAIR4ML\) IG](#)
- [Health Data Interest Group](#)
- [Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology WG \(I-ADOPT WG\)](#)
- [Metadata IG](#)
- [Metadata Standards Catalog WG](#)
- [National PID Strategies WG](#)
- [Open Science Graphs for FAIR Data IG](#)
- [Preserving Scientific Annotation WG](#)
- [Research Metadata Schemas WG](#)
- [Sensitive Data Interest Group](#)
- [Social Dynamics of Data Interoperability IG](#)
- [Vocabulary Services IG](#)
- [Wheat Data Interoperability WG](#)

 [See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#)
- [39 Hints to Facilitate the Use of Semantics for Data on Agriculture and Nutrition](#)
- [A Fresh Look at FAIR for Research Software](#)
- [A Survey on Adoption Guidelines for the FAIR4RS Principles](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model specification and guidelines](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model specification and guidelines - draft](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software \(FAIR4RS Principles\)](#)

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doi. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00086>

'Semantics, Ontology, Standardisation' cont.

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://rd-alliance.org/rdas-20th-plenary-pathways>

Version: March 2023

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Standardisation of metadata profiles, semantics and ontologies for maximising interoperability.

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS CONT.

- [Health Research Performing Organisations \(HRPOs\) FAIR Guidelines](#)
- [Member survey on bridging the gap between funders and communities - perspectives on benefits and challenges of FAIR assessments V2.0](#)
- [Metadata Standards Directory Working Group Recommendations](#)
- [Persistent identifiers Consolidated assertions](#)
- [PID Information Types \(PIT\) WG Recommendations](#)
- [Results of an Analysis of Existing FAIR Assessment Tools](#)
- [Summary of Virtual Layer Recommendations](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
- [The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies](#)
- [Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things](#)
- [Wheat Data Interoperability Recommendations](#)

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doi: <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00086>

'Data Lifecycles - Versioning, Provenance, Citation, and Reward'

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://rd-alliance.org/rdas-20th-plenary-pathways>

Version: March 2023

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Data management topics within the data lifecycle, including description, versioning, provenance, granularity, publishing, citation and reward.

RDA 20th PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 1: Data Usage Metrics WG & Repository Platforms for Research Data IG: [Practical Approaches to Tracking and Communicating the Use of Research Data](#)
- Breakout 3: Physical Samples and Collections in the Research Data Ecosystem IG: [Expanding our horizons to new disciplines: harmonising on what is core to all](#)
- Breakout 3: Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Complex Citations Working Group: [Complex Citations in the Earth and Space Sciences: Formulating Requirements for a Demonstration Prototype](#)
- Breakout 4: Data Versioning IG: [Develop actionable guidelines from the data versioning principles](#)
- Breakout 5: Data Citation WG: [Adoption Meeting of the WG on Dynamic Data Citation](#)
- Breakout 5: FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG: [IG FAIR Digital Object Fabric: Discussing the FAIR DO Concept](#)
- Breakout 6: Data Discovery Paradigms: [Recommendations for data repositories to improve data discoverability](#)
- Breakout 7: Data Granularity WG: [Data Granularity Guidance - Going Once, Going Twice,...](#)
- Breakout 7: Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC) IG: [Towards implementable recommendations: taking advantage of the SHARC open science survey](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Complex Citations Working Group](#)
- [Data Citation WG](#)
- [Data Discovery Paradigms IG](#)
- [Data Granularity WG](#)
- [Data Usage Metrics WG](#)
- [Data Versioning IG](#)
- [FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG](#)
- [Health Data Interest Group](#)
- [Physical Samples and Collections in the Research Data Ecosystem IG](#)
- [Professionalising Data Stewardship IG](#)
- [Repository Platforms for Research Data IG](#)
- [Sharing Rewards and Credit \(SHARC\) IG](#)
- [CURE-FAIR WG](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model WG](#)

☀ [See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [23 Things Physical Samples](#)
- [Compilation of Data Versioning Use cases from the RDA Data Versioning Working Group](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software \(FAIR4RS Principles\)](#)
- [Member survey on bridging the gap between funders and communities - perspectives on benefits and challenges of FAIR assessments V2.0](#)
- [Principles and best practices in data versioning for all data sets big and small](#)
- [RDA Data Usage Metrics WG Recommendations](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
- [Tromso recommendations for citation of research data in linguistics](#)
- [Versioning Data Is About More than Revisions A Conceptual Framework and Proposed Principles](#)

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'Discipline Focused Data Issues'

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://rd-alliance.org/rdas-20th-plenary-pathways>

Version: March 2023

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Implementation of principles and common data management practices from a disciplinary community.

RDA 20th PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 1: Social Science Research Data IG: [SSIG plenary meeting - Growing international coordination across social science infrastructures](#)
- Breakout 2: Life Science Data Infrastructures IG & FAIRsharing Registry: [Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG: Infrastructure supporting the FAIR data principles in life science research practice](#)
- Breakout 2: Working with PIDS in Tools: [Working with PIDS in Tools and e-infrastructures: Three concrete examples](#)
- Breakout 2: RDA/CODATA Materials Data, Infrastructure & Interoperability IG & Research Data Management in Engineering IG: [Automation of LIMS for Data Analysis and Reuse: Joint Meeting](#)
- Breakout 3: Birds of a Feather: [Data representation in materials and chemicals based on harmonised domain ontologies](#)
- Breakout 5: Birds of a Feather: [Exploring User-Centered Services for Collections as Data at the Library of Congress](#)
- Breakout 7: Chemistry Research Data IG: [Describing diverse chemistry datasets across distributed data resources](#)
- Breakout 7: IGAD Community of Practice: [Improving Global Agricultural Data \(IGAD\) Community of Practice First Steps and Way Forward](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Agrisemantics WG](#)
- [Biodiversity Data Integration IG](#)
- [Capacity Development for Agriculture Data WG](#)
- [Chemistry Research Data IG](#)
- [Data Economics IG](#)
- [Discipline-specific Guidance for Data Management Plans WG](#)
- [Geospatial IG](#)
- [Global Water Information IG](#)
- [Health Data Interest Group](#)
- [Life Science Data Infrastructures IG](#)
- [Linguistics Data IG](#)
- [Neuroimaging Data WG](#)
- [Psychological Data IG](#)
- [Raising FAIRness in health data and health research performing organisations \(HRPOs\) WG](#)
- [RDA / TDWG Metadata Standards for attribution of physical and digital collections stewardship](#)
- [RDA COVID-19](#)
- [RDA COVID-19 Epidemiology](#)
- [RDA COVID19-Legal-Ethical](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Clinical](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Community-participation](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Omics](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Social-Sciences](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Software](#)
- [RDA/CODATA Materials Data, Infrastructure & Interoperability IG](#)
- [Reproducible Health Data Services WG](#)
- [Research Data Management in Engineering IG](#)
- [Research data needs of the Photon and Neutron Science community IG](#)
- [Small Unmanned Aircraft Systems Data IG](#)
- [Social Science Research Data IG](#)
- [Wheat Data Interoperability WG](#)
- [Working Group on Ethical and Legal best practices for Drone Data in a global research context \(WELDD\)](#)
- [Working with PIDS in Tools](#)

[See all RDA groups](#)

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THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Implementation of principles and common data management practices from a disciplinary community.

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#)
- [23 Things Libraries for Research Data \(Supporting Output\)](#)
- [A Fresh Look at FAIR for Research Software](#)
- [Challenges of Curating for Reproducible and FAIR Research Output](#)
- [Health Research Performing Organisations \(HRPOs\) FAIR Guidelines](#)
- [Member survey on bridging the gap between funders and communities - perspectives on benefits and challenges of FAIR assessments V2.0](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
- [The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies](#)

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'Research Software'

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://rd-alliance.org/rdas-20th-plenary-pathways>

Version: March 2023

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Practices and policies to make software open and FAIR.

RDA 20th PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 1: Birds of a Feather: [Coordinating mechanisms for making code visible](#)
- Breakout 3: FAIR for Machine Learning (FAIR4ML) IG: [Defining the roadmap towards FAIR for Machine Learning](#)
- Breakout 3: Birds of a Feather - Computational Reproducibility: [What's Next for RDA?](#)
- Breakout 4: Software Source Code IG: [Software Source Code - policy and incentives](#)

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RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS CONT.

- [Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things](#)
 - [Use cases and identifier schemes for persistent software source code identification \(V1.1\)](#)
- [See all recommendations & outputs](#)

RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG](#)
- [FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\) WG](#)
- [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Software](#)
- [Reproducibility IG](#)
- [Software Source Code IG](#)
- [Virtual Research Environment IG \(VRE-IG\)](#)
- [FAIR for Machine Learning \(FAIR4ML\) IG](#)

 [See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#)
- [A Fresh Look at FAIR for Research Software](#)
- [A Survey on Adoption Guidelines for the FAIR4RS Principles](#)
- [Array Database Assessment Recommendations](#)
- [Challenges of Curating for Reproducible and FAIR Research Output](#)
- [Defining Research Software a controversial discussion](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software \(FAIR4RS Principles\)](#)
- [FAIR4RS Adoption support](#)
- [Summary of Virtual Layer Recommendations](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)

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Research Data Alliance Pathways: RDA 20th Plenary Synopsis

Version: March 2023

ABOUT THE PATHWAYS

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) Pathways were created by the RDA's [Technical Advisory Board](#) to help community members navigate all RDA activities. This synopsis enhances the [RDA's 20th Plenary](#) experience by providing an overview of all pathways plus their relevant Plenary sessions, RDA groups, recommendations and outputs, and ambassadors.

METHODOLOGY

Machine learning classification and clustering algorithms were employed to map RDA groups, recommendations and outputs, to the Plenary pathways. A text mining exercise was undertaken to assign a list of specific keywords to each Plenary pathway using session application texts submitted by groups in 2019 and 2020. Group charters and case statement texts, harvested from the RDA website, were mined for these keywords to map groups to the Plenary pathways. Similarly, recommendations and output texts, harvested from the RDA website and Zenodo, were mined for these keywords to map recommendations and outputs to the Plenary pathways. Not all groups, recommendations and outputs were mapped to a Plenary pathway. The data and code generated and analysed are available on [GitHub](#).

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ABOUT THE RDA

The RDA is a global organisation with over 13,000 members from 148 countries that builds social and technical bridges to enable data sharing and reuse.

[Register to become a member](#)

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